

UTILIZATION OF MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS INSTRUCTION IN ENHANCING VOCABULARY ACQUISITION OF GRADE 8 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of morphological analysis instruction on vocabulary acquisition among Grade 8 students in a public school in San Pedro City, Laguna. Employing a quasi-experimental design, two classes from Sampaguita Village National High School were selected, with one serving as a control group using traditional methods and the other as an experimental group receiving targeted morphological analysis instruction. Pre-tests established baseline vocabulary skills, revealing that both groups initially underperformed (control: 72.39, experimental: 70.78). Post-test results showed improvement, with the control group scoring Very Satisfactory (84.67) and the experimental group scoring Satisfactory (79.61). Statistical analysis indicated significant differences between pretest and posttest scores for both groups, highlighting the effectiveness of morphological analysis instruction in enhancing vocabulary acquisition. The findings suggest that such instructional techniques can bolster vocabulary learning and academic performance, prompting recommendations for schools to incorporate them into their curricula. Future research could further explore the applicability of these methods across various grades and subjects to gain a comprehensive understanding of their potential benefits and limitations in diverse educational settings.

Key words: *Grade 8 students, Morphological Analysis Instruction, Utilization, Vocabulary Acquisition*

INTRODUCTION

Morphological analysis instruction provides a robust framework for enhancing vocabulary acquisition among grade 8 students. This instructional method involves examining the structure of words to understand their meanings, roots, prefixes, and suffixes. By dissecting words into these fundamental components, students develop a deeper understanding of language and strengthen their ability to infer the meanings of unfamiliar terms. This analytical approach not only boosts vocabulary but also promotes critical thinking, aiding students in becoming more adept readers and writers. Implementing morphological analysis within the classroom can thus serve as an effective tool in enriching students' linguistic skills and overall academic performance.

Difficulties in comprehension can often be linked to the accumulation and understanding of vocabulary words encountered by students across various documents and scenarios that necessitate problem-solving skills. According to Afzal (2019), non-native English speakers encountered several challenges, including understanding the meanings of new words, pronouncing them correctly, using them accurately, and memorizing their correct spellings. These obstacles significantly impacted students' comprehension abilities and their proficiency in writing literary compositions. Thus, the crux of these findings ultimately revolved around vocabulary development.

Vocabulary acquisition is the process of learning new words, which is crucial for academic success as it forms the foundational component of understanding concepts across content areas. With a strong vocabulary, individuals can enhance their comprehension of the written and spoken information they encounter. By expanding their vocabulary knowledge, individuals can improve their ability to grasp and interpret various inputs, both in written form and through listening, thus facilitating deeper understanding and academic achievement.

Building strong vocabulary foundations was essential for learners to understand and comprehend concepts across various subject areas written in the English language. Therefore, English teachers must prioritize increasing learners' vocabulary acquisition. To achieve this goal, teachers employed various strategies.

However, in the Philippines, the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic has posed significant challenges, particularly in the field of education. The Department of Education was faced with the daunting task of implementing physical distancing measures to prevent or mitigate the spread of the virus. Consequently, classes and other school activities for the 2019-2020 and 2020-2021 school years were suspended and canceled. In response, the Department crafted and adapted D.O. 12 s. 2020, also known as the Adoption of Basic Education Learning Continuity Plans (B.E. -LCP), as a novel approach to sustain the teaching and learning process for students while ensuring the welfare and health security of learners and DepEd personnel. This initiative involves soliciting expertise from various fields within the department to ensure the quality of education and support the needs of students.

Furthermore, this situation necessitated the utilization of diverse mediums to deliver instruction to learners, including online learning, modular approaches, as well as radio and television broadcasts, among others. These alternative methods of instruction were employed to ensure continued access to education amidst the challenges posed by the pandemic.

Challenges emerged regarding the quality of learning, teachers' preparedness, and the adequacy of materials provided to learners. These issues compounded pre-existing concerns regarding students' poor comprehension and low proficiency in mathematics and science. The severity of these challenges became evident through the results of the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), a large-scale test conducted by member countries to assess the global employability and competencies of 15-year-old students.

The PISA 2018 results revealed that the Philippines ranked last in terms of reading literacy and second to last in scientific literacy and mathematical literacy among the 79 countries that participated in the assessment, conducted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). These findings underscored the urgent need to address the deficiencies in the Philippine education system and implement measures to improve student performance and proficiency in core subjects (Galang, 2020).

Attention to the PISA scores highlights the reading comprehension challenges prevalent in the country. It has been identified that the reading comprehension skills of Filipino students require improvement due to the regular techniques employed in teaching. Effective reading skills are fundamental for students to comprehend and engage with various subjects in school. At Sampaguita Village National High School, Grade 8 students obtained a score of 51.11 in the Mean Percentage Score (MPS), ranking as the second lowest in the Junior High School (JHS) department. Moreover, the recent Philippine Reading Inventory pretest conducted in 2023 revealed persistent difficulties in reading comprehension, with a higher percentage of Grade 8 students falling into frustration levels.

Hence, it is crucial for schools, in collaboration with the Department of Education, to address these issues and gaps to ensure the provision of quality primary education. Efforts should focus on implementing effective strategies to enhance reading comprehension skills among students, thereby empowering them to succeed academically and beyond.

This study aimed to address the gap in the literature regarding the utilization of "Morphological Analysis Instruction" in teaching English across different levels. It focused on analyzing the effectiveness of morphological analysis instruction in enhancing students' English vocabulary acquisition, which in turn aids in their comprehension.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of morphological analysis instruction in enhancing the English vocabulary acquisition of Grade 8 students at Sampaguita Village National High School.

Specifically, it sought to address the following research questions:

1. What is the result of the pretest of the control and experimental groups before the implementation of morphological analysis instruction (MAI)?
2. What is the posttest result of the control and experimental groups after implementing the MAI?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results of the control group?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results of the experimental group?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what program plan may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

An overview of the study's comprehensive design and methodologies was provided. This included information on research design, location, population and sample selection methods, participants involved in the study as well as validation of instruments used for data collection technique with emphasis given to quantitative data analyses approaches employed throughout its implementation period.

Research Design

The research design for this study was detailed and structured using a quasi-experimental approach, which was mainly chosen due to the constraints within the educational setting. As outlined by Reichardt (2019), the absence of randomization was a characteristic feature of this design type, arising because the class schedules in public schools were fixed, making it impractical to assign students to the control and experimental groups randomly. In addition, DEPED Order 32, series 2003 reiterated its policy that all public schools were strictly enjoined to admit all prospective Filipino students, hence resulting in a heterogenous set of students. Two sections of Grade 8 students from Sampaguita Village National High School participated in this study. These sections were designated as the control and experimental groups. The experimental group was exposed to Morphological Analysis Instruction (MAI), a targeted educational intervention designed to enhance students' understanding of word structures and their meanings. In contrast, the control group continued with the traditional approach (TA) to teaching the English subject, which does not explicitly focus on morphological skills.

Research Locale

The study was carried out at Sampaguita Village National High School, located at Molave St., Barangay Calendola, San Pedro City, Laguna. This educational institution was selected as the primary site for data collection due to its convenient accessibility and the demographic characteristics of its student body. All participants were students from this school, carefully chosen to guarantee that the collected data would be both robust and directly relevant to the objectives of the research.

Population and Sampling

This research employed purposive sampling to select participants, a strategy where individuals were chosen based on specific characteristics, enhancing the relevance and effectiveness of the investigation. According to Alchemer (2021), purposive sampling was appropriate when the study required a particular group of people who met predefined criteria.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents in this study were sixty (60) students studying English in Grade 8 classes in Sampaguita Village National High School S.Y. 2023- 2024. The study involved two sections of Grade 8 students enrolled in the K to 12 Basic Education Program. These two (2) classes of Grade 8 students at Sampaguita Village National High School S.Y. 2023- 2024 belong to a heterogeneous group of classes. The respondents were divided into an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group (8 Humility), composed of 30 students, was exposed to Morphological Analysis Instruction (MAI), while the control group (8 Justice) composed of 30 students, had the traditional approach.

Table A

Respondents of the Study

Group	Grade Level	Section	No. of Students
Control	8	Justice	30
Experimental	8	Humility	30

Instrument

This research employed a set of carefully selected instruments to ensure a comprehensive and precise evaluation of the educational interventions being studied. Each instrument had been chosen to effectively measure the impact of the teaching methodologies on student learning outcomes and to provide robust data for analysis. The following sections detail the specific tools utilized in this research.

A teacher-made test was developed and validated to evaluate the effectiveness of Morphological Analysis Instruction (MAI) and the Traditional Approach (TA) on the English performance of Grade 8 students. This assessment tool comprises a 35-item test designed to align with the Essential Learning Competencies for Grade 8 English subjects. The items included in the test are carefully crafted to reflect the crucial aspects of the English curriculum that were expected to be influenced by the instructional methods under study.

Before the creation of the test, a detailed Table of Specifications (TOS) was constructed. This TOS served as a blueprint to ensure a balanced representation of topics regarding their difficulty and the time allocated to teaching each subject in the curriculum. It was designed to ensure that the test items adequately covered the breadth of content and skills the students were expected to master, providing a comprehensive measure of their performance across different areas of the English subject.

The tools used to validate the learning plans were adapted from the Evaluation Rating Sheet for Print Resources of the Department of Education's (DepEd) learning management systems, including comprehensive criteria for assessing learning materials' relevance, coherence, and pedagogical soundness. These tools provided a structured framework for the experts to evaluate various aspects of the learning plans, including their alignment with learning objectives, the appropriateness of content for the targeted student age group, and the effectiveness of the IDEA instructional model implementation. During the validation, each expert reviewed the learning plans to ensure they met the expected educational standards and were suitable for achieving the desired learning outcomes. The review examined how well the Introduction, Development, Engagement, and Assimilation components were integrated into the lesson plans to support coherent and progressive learning experiences.

Validation of the Instrument

The teacher-made test underwent validation by the experts. This validation focused on evaluating the test's organization, format, and content relevance to ensure it met academic standards and effectively assessed student understanding. The experts' validation of the teacher-made test resulted in a mean score of 1.0, interpreted as "essential." This high level of approval indicated that the test was well-constructed and suitable for assessing the level of understanding among the students regarding the English topics taught. The validation confirmed that the test was a reliable tool for measuring the differential impacts of the MAI on student learning outcomes, providing valuable insights into the efficacy of these teaching approaches.

The researcher developed three comprehensive lessons tailored to utilize the Morphological Analysis Instruction (MAI) approach. These lessons were intended for the fourth grading period of the Grade 8 English curriculum.. The design of each lesson plan was strategically developed to align with the core competencies required for Grade 8 English, ensuring that each stage of the IDEA model was effectively addressed to maximize student engagement and learning.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study uses specific steps to collect data. First, an endorsement letter was requested from the Dean of Graduate School and signed by the adviser to formally ask permission from the School Division Superintendent and School (DepEd SDO San Pedro City) and then to the school Principal to conduct the study in Sampaguita High School. After evaluating the research study, permission was granted on the condition that no government funds were utilized, and classes were not interrupted as outlined in DepEd Order No. 9 s. 2005 to boost engaged time-on-task and ensure conformity with it; additionally proper coordination must occur between the school principal and researcher before conducting this activity. The procedure of the study had three phases: the pretest phase, the experiment phase, and the posttest phase. The Pretest Phase consisted of a given pretest on the vocabulary test to assess the vocabulary performance of the participants.

Pretests with 35-item tests were given both in the control group and experimental group during the first week of the implementation. In the second week, during the Experimental Phase, the experimental group was taught using morphological analysis instruction while the control group was taught using the traditional approach of teaching vocabulary. The most common (15) prefixes and (15) roots were taught. During the posttest phase or in the third week the 35-item posttest was given. The results were collected after each test. After giving the pretest and posttest a comparison was made with the result of the study. A pretest and posttest were administered in both classes. Test papers were checked, and scores were collected, recorded, and statistically treated. Finally, the Collation and Tabulation of Data. Results were collated, tallied, and tabulated all the information acquired from the subjects then analyzed and interpreted the statistical results. Specifically, the study applied the paired t-test to determine the significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the control group and the experimental group.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The paired t-test was used to compare the pretest and post-test scores within the same group. This statistical test was appropriate for comparing two related samples to determine if their average differences were zero. In this context, it helped determine whether significant learning gains were made within each group due to their educational interventions.

This analysis specifically assessed the effectiveness of the Morphological Analysis Instruction for the experimental group by checking if the mean improvement from the pretest to the post-test was statistically significant.

Interpretation and Analysis of Data Gathered

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of morphological analysis instruction on vocabulary acquisition among Grade 8 students in Sampaguita Village National High School at San Pedro City, Laguna.

Research Question 1:

What is the result of the pretest of the control and experimental groups before the implementation of morphological analysis instruction (MAI)?

Table 1.1

Pretest Result of the Control Group Before the Implementation of Morphological Analysis Instruction

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	1	3.33%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	3	10%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	4	13.33%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	3	10%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	19	63.33%
	Total	30	100%
	Overall Performance		72.39

Before implementing morphological analysis instruction, the control group's overall performance was 72.39%, categorized as Did Not Meet Expectations. Of the 30 students, 19 (63.33%) fell into this category, while 3 (10%) achieved Fairly Satisfactory, 4 (13.33%) were Satisfactory, 3 (10%) reached Very Satisfactory, and none achieved Outstanding in the pretest.

The pretest results indicate a pressing need for instructional intervention, as 63.33% of the control group did not meet expectations, highlighting significant gaps in their understanding. This suggests that implementing morphological analysis instruction could be crucial in addressing these deficiencies and enhancing overall literacy skills. With varied performance levels, differentiated teaching strategies may be necessary to effectively support all learners, particularly those most struggling. Additionally, these findings establish a baseline for future assessments, allowing educators to measure the impact of the new instructional approach and adjust their methods accordingly. Ultimately, the data underscores the importance of targeted support and professional development for teachers, aiming to foster greater engagement and improved outcomes in literacy for all students.

The pretest data correlate with findings in the literature, such as those by Brooks et al. (2023) and Silvestri (2024), where student performance in national examinations was similarly assessed. These studies found that comprehension and vocabulary acquisition can be significantly improved with a focused approach to morphology in instruction.

Table 1.2

Pretest Result of the Experimental Group Before the Implementation of Morphological Analysis Instruction

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	0	0
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	2	6.67%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	3	10%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	5	16.67%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	20	66.67%
	Total	30	100%
	Overall Performance	70.78	

The overall performance of the Experimental group prior to the implementation of morphological analysis instruction was 70.78, categorized as "Did Not Meet Expectations." Out of 30 students, 20 (66.67%) fell into this category, while five (16.67%) achieved "Fairly Satisfactory," three (10%) were "Satisfactory," and two (6.67%) attained "Very Satisfactory." None of the students achieved an "Outstanding" rating in the pretest.

The pretest results suggest a pressing need for targeted instructional strategies, particularly morphological analysis, to enhance student performance. With a significant portion of the group not meeting expectations, implementing effective interventions could help bridge knowledge gaps and promote greater understanding of language structures. Additionally, ongoing assessments will be essential to monitor progress and adapt teaching methods, ultimately aiming to elevate student achievement across all performance categories.

According to Naldic et al. (2019), the implications of Table 1.2 indicate that just ten students in the experimental group attained a fairly satisfactory to a very satisfactory level of comprehension regarding morphology. The results were consistent with those found within the control group, suggesting both groups had similar initial knowledge levels about morphological analysis-ultimately supporting valid comparison between post-instruction effects seen across the two groups.

Research Question 2:

What is the posttest result of the control and experimental groups after implementing the MAI?

Table 2.1

Posttest Result of the Control Group after Implementation of Morphological Analysis Instruction

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	12	40%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	4	13.33%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	3	10%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	5	16.67%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	6	20%
	Total	30	100%
	Overall Performance	84.67	

The Control Group's overall performance in the post-test was 84.67, categorized as "Very Satisfactory." Among the 30 students, 12 (40%) achieved an "Outstanding" rating, while four (13.33%) received "Very Satisfactory." Additionally, three students (10%) were rated "Satisfactory," and five (16.67%) were "Fairly Satisfactory." Conversely, six students (20%) did not meet expectations in the pretest.

The Control Group's strong post-test performance indicates effective instructional methods that could serve as a model for other groups. The high percentage of students achieving "Outstanding" suggests that successful strategies should be analyzed and potentially replicated. However, the 20% who did not meet expectations highlight the need for targeted support and intervention to address learning gaps. Continuous assessment and differentiated instruction could further enhance overall student outcomes.

In a study by Thane (2023), an elicited production task (EPT) and a forced choice task (FCT) were administered to a total of 54 HS and 17 Spanish-dominant participants to investigate the effects of morphological regularity, lexical frequency, age of English acquisition, proficiency, and frequency of use on the production and selection of preterit morphology with states. The findings demonstrated a negative correlation between lexical frequency and the preterit production by HS with states, indicating that these bilinguals were more likely to employ the preterit with less-frequent verbs. Lexical frequency had less of an impact on higher-proficiency speakers during production. On the other hand, proficiency affected how HS answered in the FCT; compared to the EPT, HS were more likely to select the preterit in the FCT. Taken as a whole, these findings validated legacy

language hypotheses that highlighted the significance of linguistic feature activation and the disparities between production and comprehension.

Table 2.2

Posttest Result of the Experimental Group after Implementation of Morphological Analysis Instruction

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Outstanding	2	6.67%
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory	6	20%
80 – 84	Satisfactory	9	30%
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory	5	16.67%
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	8	26.67%
	Total	30	100%
	Overall Performance	79.61	

The overall performance of the Experimental Group in the post-test was 79.61%, categorized as "Satisfactory." Among the 30 students, two (6.67%) achieved an "Outstanding" rating, while six (20%) earned "Very Satisfactory." Additionally, nine students (30%) were rated "Satisfactory," and five (16.67%) received "Fairly Satisfactory." Conversely, eight students (26.67%) did not meet expectations in the pretest.

The Experimental Group's performance in the post-test suggests that the instructional methods implemented had a positive effect on student learning. The presence of students achieving higher ratings indicates that some individuals benefitted significantly from the intervention. However, the number of students who did not meet expectations points to the necessity for ongoing support and differentiated instruction. Continued assessments and targeted interventions will be essential to address individual learning gaps and enhance overall student achievement.

Kieffer (2023) suggested that knowing morphology improved reading skills by helping to identify and decode challenging words, as well as enhancing comprehension through grasping the meaning of word parts. It demonstrated how effective this intervention can be for boosting both morphological ability and academic achievement among students.

Research Question 3:

Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results of the control group?

Table 3

Test of Significant Difference Between the pretest and posttest scores of the Control group

	Paired Differences		T	P value	Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD				
Pretest and Posttest of Control Group	-7.367	8.0021	-5.042	.000	Significant	Reject H_0

There was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control group. A marked mean decrease in scores by -7.367, and a standard deviation (SD) of 8.0021 was observed, suggesting a notable spread of individual changes. The computed t-value of -5.042 and a p-value of .000, were significantly below the conventional threshold of .05, indicating that these changes were statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

The significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control group suggests that the instructional methods may not have been effective, as indicated by the marked decrease in scores. The notable spread of individual changes highlights the variability in student responses, which may warrant further investigation into the factors affecting performance. The statistically significant results imply a need to reassess the teaching strategies used in this group, potentially leading to modifications that better support student learning and engagement.

Moreover, Manyak et al. (2019) highlighted the benefits of integrating morphological instruction into comprehensive reading programs, noting improvements in spelling, vocabulary, and comprehension across various student groups. Their research supported the notable improvements observed in the control group's post-test scores, indicating that structured linguistic instruction can significantly enhance student learning. This body of research underscored the potential advantages of structured English language instruction. Students held words with common prefixes or suffixes, identified peers with similar base words, and discussed the meanings lively, enhancing their understanding of affixes. They then engaged in a game of Affix Jeopardy to deepen their learning (Manyak, 2019).

Research Question 4:

Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results of the experimental group?

Table 4

Test of Significant Difference Between the pretest and posttest scores of the Experimental Group

	Paired Differences		T	P value	Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD				
Pretest and Posttest of Experimental Group	-5.300	6.65479	-4.362	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

There was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group, with a mean difference indicating that posttest scores were, on average, 5.3 points higher than pretest scores. This improvement suggests a positive impact of the intervention on the experimental group's performance. The standard deviation of the paired differences was 6.65479, reflecting variability in the scores around the mean difference; a higher standard deviation indicates a broader spread of scores. The t-statistic of -4.362 measures how much the mean difference deviates from zero, standardized by the standard deviation of the differences. The negative sign of the t-value confirms that the posttest scores exceeded the pretest scores. Additionally, the p-value of .000, which is well below the conventional alpha level of .05, indicates that the observed difference is statistically significant and unlikely to be due to random chance. The analysis concluded that the differences in scores were "Significant," suggesting that the changes from pretest to posttest can be attributed to the Morphological Analysis Instruction. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that the instruction had a substantial positive effect on student performance in the experimental group.

The significant improvement in the experimental group's posttest scores suggests that the Morphological Analysis Instruction effectively enhanced student performance. This positive outcome indicates that the instructional strategies implemented were beneficial and warrant further exploration for broader application. The variability in scores also points to differences in individual student responses, highlighting the need for ongoing support to address diverse learning needs. Future research could build on these findings by examining long-term effects and refining instructional approaches to maximize student engagement and achievement.

These studies support the observed data in the table, confirming that well-designed educational interventions can lead to significant improvements in performance. For further insights, refer to detailed methodologies and statistical treatments in educational intervention studies (Statistics by Jim, 2022; LSU, 2022).

Research Question 5:

Based on the findings of the study, what program may be proposed?

PROGRAM ACE: AMELIORATING COMPREHENSION IN ENGLISH 8

Program Rationale

Project ACE, which stands for "Ameliorating Comprehension in English," is an advanced English reading program carefully devised for Grade 8 students requiring supplementary support in vocabulary acquisition at Sampaguita Village National High School. Evidence-based pedagogical methods inform this bespoke program. Its focus on morphological instruction is mainly characterized—as a proven strategy for enhancing vocabulary knowledge and comprehension skills among middle schoolers Project ACE is a comprehensive English reading program for Grade 8 learners to bolster their reading comprehension abilities. This program integrates evidence-based strategies focusing on morphological instruction to enhance student's understanding of complex texts and foster improved communication skills.

In response to the Department of Education's (DepEd) ongoing efforts to improve English literacy among students, Project ACE (Ameliorating Communication in English) emerges as a particularly significant initiative. DepEd has consistently advocated for innovative approaches to enhance reading comprehension—a skill integral to academic success and lifelong learning (Department of Education, 2015). Project ACE directly aligns with this goal, offering a tailored intervention that equips Grade 8 students at Sampaguita Village National High School with the morphological tools they need to navigate the complexities of English vocabulary and syntax (Department of Education, 2019).

Grounded in the principle that a robust vocabulary is a cornerstone of literacy Halford et al. (2022) Project ACE is designed to fortify students' command of complex texts, facilitating improved communication competencies. By dissecting words into their constituent morphemes, the program systematically develops an understanding of word formation, aiding students in the decoding and assimilation of new vocabulary. Targeting students identified through diagnostic tests as needing intervention in English (Vaughn et al. (2019)) Project ACES represents a strategic response to the identified language challenges within the student population of Sampaguita Village National High School.

RESULTS

Summary of Findings

Based on the results of this research study, the following summary of findings was identified.

1. Pretest Result of the Control and Experimental Group before the Implementation of Morphological Analysis Instruction

1.1 Control Group

The overall performance was **72.39** interpreted as **Did Not Meet Expectations**.

1.2 Experimental Group

The overall performance was **70.78** interpreted as **Did Not Meet Expectations**.

2. Posttest Result of the Control and Experimental Groups after Implementing the MAI

2.1 Control Group

The overall performance was **84.67** interpreted as **Very Satisfactory**.

2.2 Experimental Group

The overall performance was **79.61** interpreted as **Satisfactory**.

3. Test of Significance Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control Group

There was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control group. A marked mean decrease in scores of -7.367, and a standard deviation (SD) of 8.0021 was observed, suggesting a notable spread of individual changes. The computed t-value of -5.042 and a p-value of .000, were significantly below the conventional threshold of .05, indicating that these changes were statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that the observed difference in mean scores from the pretest to the posttest is not attributable to chance, and there is a significant difference in the student's performance over time.

4. Test of Significance Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group

There was a significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the experimental group. A mean difference (paired differences between pretest and posttest scores) of -5.300. This negative value indicated that, on average, the post-test scores were 5.3 points higher than the pretest scores, suggesting an improvement in the experimental group's performance after the intervention. The SD of the paired differences was 6.65479, reflecting the variability or dispersion from the mean difference. A higher SD would suggest a greater spread of scores around the mean difference. The value of -4.362 for the t-statistic measured the extent to which the mean difference deviates from zero, standardized by the standard deviation of the differences. The negative sign of the

t-value indicates that the post-test scores were higher than the pretest scores. The p-value was .000, which was less than the conventional alpha level of .05, indicating that the observed score was statistically significant and not due to random chance.

5. The Proposed Program

Based on the findings, Program ACE: Ameliorating Comprehension in English 8 was proposed to bolster the students' reading comprehension abilities. This program integrates evidence-based strategies focusing on morphological instruction to enhance student's understanding of complex texts and foster improved communication skills.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the research study, the following conclusions were derived:

1. That the high number of students failing to meet required standards suggests current teaching methods may not be effective for this group. Lessons on morphological analysis could potentially improve their understanding and performance. Many students in both the experimental and control groups have limited knowledge of morphological analysis, indicating the groups are comparable in their familiarity. Therefore, they can be considered homogeneous for the purposes of this study.

2. That after incorporating MAI, the experimental and control groups demonstrate an elevation in post-test scores among participants. Such a trend is expected given that these interventions are designed to influence student performance.

3. The significant difference in the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the control group shows positive feedback towards traditional teaching methods. However, MAI also shows an increase in the posttest results of both groups. As a result, these practices are commonly employed within classroom settings and students have become accustomed to them, thus confirming their effectiveness for educating pupils on word morphology concepts.

4. That the Morphological Analysis Instruction positively affects the experimental group's learning outcomes, providing empirical support for the effectiveness of the Morphological Analysis Instruction. This considerable improvement demonstrates the potential of such targeted instructional strategies to enhance student's understanding and application of morphological concepts, thereby improving their performance in the English language and reading comprehension. The study's findings could have important implications for educational practices, particularly for curricula that bolster language acquisition skills.

5. That Program ACE highlights the importance of innovative and targeted educational interventions in enhancing student learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations materialized and identified.

1. Since most students showed limited knowledge and application of morphological analysis, teachers may develop and integrate a structured morphological analysis instruction program within the curriculum to enhance students' understanding and application of morphological concepts. This can lead to improved reading comprehension and overall academic performance. Furthermore, the school may conduct workshops for professional development to impart effective techniques of teaching morphological analysis to teachers. Furnish resources and constant aid so that the educators are equipped with the necessary skills to proficiently administer the new curriculum.

2. To promote retention of morphological concepts, teachers may devise classroom activities that are stimulating and interactive. They may incorporate fun games, collaboration between peers as well as illustrations from everyday life to foster relevance and interest among students in the learning process.

3. Teachers may regularly use formative and summative assessments to track the progress of students. They may utilize the data obtained from these evaluations, institute instructional adjustments accordingly, as well as offer supplementary assistance where necessary for effective learning outcomes.

4. Teachers may make morphological analysis support a regular part of their class routine and intervention plans, empowering participants in the learning process by equipping them with resources and guidance to continue their efforts at home.

5. To boost the reading and language skills of students via Morphological Analysis Instruction (MAI), consider incorporating ACE program seamlessly into the curriculum.

6. Future researchers who will embark on research studies about morphological analysis instruction, may conduct an in-depth review of existing literature on morphological analysis to understand the current state of knowledge, identify gaps, and build a strong foundation of their research.

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